

SiC FIBER REINFORCED HIGH FORMABILITY TITANIUM ALLOY COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Interfacial reaction between fiber and matrix of titanium matrix composites (TMCs) during fabrication is often considered to degrade the properties of the composite. One of the most effective means to suppress the reaction is to lower the fabrication temperature. In this study, high formability titanium alloy (SP-700) from NKK Corporation was chosen as matrix so as to lower the fabrication temperature while continuous silicon carbide fiber (SCS-6) from Textron Specialty Materials was chosen as reinforcement. The fabrication temperature was varied from 973K to 1173K to consolidate SCS-6/SP-700 by HIPing with constant fabrication time (2hr) and constant fabrication pressure (150MPa). As a result, 1023K, which is about 150K lower than the fabrication temperature of other titanium alloy matrix composites, is found to be high enough to consolidate SCS-6/SP-700 in good state and to give the highest tensile strength of the composite. This large fabrication temperature drop might be due to the excellent superplastic formability of SP-700.

1.INTRODUCTION

It is believed that titanium matrix composites (TMCs) could yield significant performance advantages in gas-generator because of their high strength and stiffness. TMCs, however, have some difficulties for use in gas-generator such as properties degradation caused by interfacial reactions during fabrication, high-cost process to manufacture composite parts and lacking of data for designing etc. One of the most attractive solutions to some of those difficulties is to lower the fabrication temperature.

The fabrication temperature deeply depends on the matrix alloy compositions. For example the fabrication temperature of SiC/Ti-6Al-4V is about 1143K⁽¹⁾. Those of SiC/Ti-15V-3Cr-3Al-3Sn and SiC/Ti-6Al-2Sn-4Zr-2Mo are 1153K and 1203K respectively^(2,3). The fabrication temperature is usually decided to be the lowest temperature to consolidate matrix alloy in good state in order to avoid excess interfacial reactions which are more severe as the fabrication temperature increases and degrade the composite in general. The consolidation process of matrix alloy is divided into two stages, plastic deformation and diffusion bonding. Thus it is expected that the higher formability alloy gives lower fabrication temperature of the TMC.

In this study, relatively new titanium alloy, so called SP-700, is chosen as matrix alloy because of its high formability⁴⁾. The objective of this work is to decide the fabrication temperature of SP-700 matrix composite by investigating the interfacial reaction kinetics and tensile properties of composites consolidated at various temperature and to see how much the fabrication temperature is lowered.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

High formability titanium alloy (SP-700) from NKK Corporation was used for matrix alloy. The nominal composition of SP-700 is Ti-4.5Al-3V-2Fe-2Mo(wt%). Continuous silicon fiber (SCS-6) with thick carbon layer on the surface from Textron Specialty Materials was used for reinforcement. Sheets of woven fabric SCS-6 and sheets of 120 μ m SP-700 were alternatively piled up one layer by one. The sandwiched bodies in 4-ply unidirectional lay-ups were packed in sealing metal containers and were HIPed to be consolidated. Fabrication temperature of SCS-6/SP-700 were varied from 973K to 1173K with constant fabrication time (2hr) and constant fabrication pressure (150MPa). Laminations of SP-700 sheets were also consolidated so as to be for reference.

Both consolidations of SCS-6/SP-700 composites and SP-700 monolithic were submitted to metallurgical inspection and subjected to tensile tests and fractography investigation. All consolidations were evaluated as fabricated (as HIPed).

A set of SCS-6/SP-700 composites consolidated by HIPing at 1023K for 2 hr with argon gas at 150MPa were subjected to heat treatments at 1073K, 1123K and 1173K in vacuum changing the holding time from one hour to 8 hours. These heat treated samples were submitted to metallurgical inspection to investigate the interfacial reaction mechanisms.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Microstructure

Microstructures of 120 μ m SP-700 sheet as received and SCS-6/SP-700 composites consolidated at various temperature (973K, 1023K, 1048K, 1073K, 1173K) for 2 hr with argon gas at 150MPa are shown in Fig.1 and 2. SP-700 as received has ultra-fine grains and the grains of SCS-6/SP-700 become larger with increasing the fabrication temperature up to 1073K while SCS-6/SP-700 consolidated at 1173K, which is just above β transus, shows acicular structure. Both of SCS-6/SP-700 composites consolidated at 973K and 1023K show almost the same microstructures. However, bonding between fiber and metal consolidated at 973K seems not sufficient, while that consolidated at 1023K is good enough. This was ascertained by the fact that machining the composites fabricated at 973K

Fig. 1 Microstructures of SP-700 sheet as received

to specimen coupons resulted in breaking down, whereas ones fabricated at 1023K were successfully machined to coupons. Reaction products at the interface of SCS-6/SP-700 fabricated at 1023K seems negligible and those of SCS-6/SP-700 fabricated at 1048K are recognized. The reaction zone thickness increases as fabrication temperature increases.

Fig.2 Microstructures of SCS-6/SP-700 consolidated at various temperature for 2 hr with argon gas at 150MPa.

Fig.3 shows some of microstructures of SCS-6/SP-700 consolidated at 1073K and followed by heat treatment in vacuum for various time. An investigation of interfacial reaction kinetics between fiber and metal is summarized in Fig.4 which shows the relationship between reaction zone thickness and the square root of holding time at each heat treatment temperature. Reaction zone thickness increases with increasing heat treatment temperature and heat treatment time. Besides Fig.4 shows a linear relationship. Thus the reaction zone growth kinetics can be modeled with parabolic growth law. So the temperature dependent rate constant, K , follows Arrhenius relation and the apparent activation energy can be calculated from the slope of a linear relationship between $\ln(k)$ and $1/T$. However, the slope is not linear for the temperature range of this examination as shown in Fig.5. This can be considered that K below the β transus is different from K above β transus. More data are needed for determining K .

(a) Heat treated at 1123K for 1 hr

(b) Heat treated at 1123K for 4 hr

(c) Heat treated at 1123K for 8 hr

Fig.3 Microstructures of SCS-6/SP-700 heat treated at 1123K for various hours after consolidation at 1023K for 2 hr with argon gas at 150MPa.

Fig.4 Reaction zone thickness as a function of square root of holding time for heat treatment

Fig.5 Arrhenius plot of the $\ln(K)$ vs. $1/T$

3.2 Tensile properties

Tensile test results of both SCS-6/SP-700 and SP-700 monolithic consolidated at various temperature are summarized in Fig.6 and 7. The strength in longitudinal direction to fiber orientation of SCS-6/SP-700 consolidated at 1023K shows the highest value and the strength decreases with increasing the fabrication temperature up to 1073K, while the strength of SCS-6/SP-700 consolidated at 973K could not be evaluated due to the insufficient consolidation as mentioned above. The strength of SCS-6/SP-700 consolidated at 1173K showed almost the same values as that consolidated at 1073K. On the other hand both strength in transverse direction to fiber orientation of SCS-6/SP-700 and strength of SP-700 monolithic showed constant values, 600MPa and 1000MPa respectively. And both Young modulus of SCS-6/SP-700 composite and SP-700 monolithic are independent of consolidation temperature.

Fig. 6 Strength of SCS-6/SP-700 and SP-700 as a function of consolidation temperature

Fig.7 Young modulus of SCS-6/SP-700 and SP-700 as a function of consolidation temperature

Fig. 8 shows scanning electron microscope (SEM) micrographs of fracture surfaces of tensile test specimens from SCS-6/SP-700 fabricated at 1023K, 1048K, 1073K and 1173K.

(a) Fracture surfaces of SCS-6/SP-700 composite consolidated at 1023K

(b) Fracture surfaces of SCS-6/SP-700 composite consolidated at 1048K

(c) Fracture surfaces of SCS-6/SP-700 composite consolidated at 1073K

(d) Fracture surfaces of SCS-6/SP-700 composite fabricated at 1173K

Fig. 8 SEM micrographs of fracture surfaces of tensile test specimens from SCS-6/SP-700

Pulling out of fibers is observed on all fracture surfaces of composites. The fracture surface of the matrix component exhibits the features of a material that failed in a ductile manner. Elongated dimples are observed on most area of the surface and shear dimples are observed a little near interfaces indicating that matrix component fracture occurs in shear mode close to the interface and in tensile mode in the rest of it.

The difference among the fracture surfaces of composites fabricated at different temperature is scarcely distinguished or negligible, while the strength of composites varied with the fabrication temperature changing from 1023K to 1073K as shown in Fig. 6. Besides the strength of SP-700 monolithic consolidated at various temperature showed constant values. These suggest that fracture of matrix followed the fracture of fibers resulting in no change of fractography of composites and that interfacial reaction products degrade the fiber strength resulting in decrease of the strength of SCS-6/SP-700 composite. Even though details of fracture mechanism of SCS-6/SP-700 composite could not be revealed in this study, it is concluded that 1023K was the best temperature for fabricating SCS-6/SP-700 composite. The fabrication temperature, 1023K, is much lower than those of other titanium matrix composites. This large fabrication temperature drop, about 150K, might be due to the excellent superplastic formability of SP-700. This can be quite effective on minimizing the interfacial reaction and on saving fabrication costs of TMCs parts.

Fig.9 shows the strength of SCS-6/SP-700 composite and SP-700 monolithic up to 773K. Both were consolidated at 1023K. SCS-6/SP-700 composite retains its strength well up to 773K and its density is lower than that of matrix. Thus SCS-6/SP-700 can be used extensively for gas-generator.

Fig.9 Strength of SCS-6/SP/700 composite and SP-700 monolithic consolidated at 1023K vs. temperature

4. CONCLUSION

In this paper, high formability titanium alloy, SP-700 (Ti-4.5Al-3V-2Fe-2Mo), was used for matrix of titanium matrix composite and the fabrication temperature of the composite was decided by investigating the interfacial reaction kinetics and tensile properties of composites consolidated at 973K, 1023K, 1048K, 1073K and 1173K with constant fabrication time and constant fabrication pressure. The following conclusions can be obtained.

- 1) 1023K, which is about 150K lower than the fabrication temperature of other titanium alloy matrix composites, is high enough to consolidate SCS-6/SP-700 in good state and to give the highest tensile strength of the composite.
- 2) Reaction zone growth kinetics at the interface between SCS-6 fiber and SP-700 matrix can be modeled with parabolic growth law.
- 3) Pulling out of fibers is observed on fracture surface of composite. The matrix component of composite exhibits ductile fracture features.
- 4) SCS-6/SP-700 composite fabricated at 1023K retains its strength well up to 773K and can be used extensively for gas-generator.

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